

INNOVATION VS COMPETENCY? UNLOCKING THE PATH OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION TO INDONESIA'S MSME PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the factors influencing the business performance (BP) of MSMEs in Indonesia, through the lens of the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT). This study addresses the gap by examining the effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) on BP through Innovation Capability (IC) and Entrepreneurial Competency (EC), and by testing the moderating role of External Environment (EE) in these relationships. The research adopts a quantitative approach using survey data collected from 340 relocated MSME actors. Data were analyzed with Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The main findings reveal that EO does not directly affect BP, but significantly influences it through the mediators IC and EC. Both IC and EC were found to have a positive effect on BP. Furthermore, EE acts as a negative moderator, weakening the relationship between IC and BP as well as EC and BP, but does not moderate the EO–BP relationship.

Keywords: MSMEs, Entrepreneurial Orientation, Innovation Capability, Entrepreneurial Competency, External Environment, Business Performance.

JEL: L1; L26; L53

1. INTRODUCTION

MSMEs in Indonesia play a highly vital role in sustaining the national economy. Data show that in 2019 there were 65, 4 million MSME units that contributed to the absorption of 123, 3 thousand workers (Kemenkeu DJPB, 2023). In 2023, the contribution of MSMEs to Gross Domestic Product reached 61 percent while absorbing 97 percent of the total Indonesian workforce (Good Stats, 2024). These figures affirm MSMEs as the backbone of the national economy stability. Nevertheless, in 2024 the MSME sector faced a phenomenon of business expansion slowdown. The MSME Business Index in the first quarter of 2024 stood at 102, 9. A decline of 0, 1 points compared with the previous quarter and it further decreased to the level of 102, 6 in the third quarter of 2024 (Kumparan, 2024). This downward trend indicates persistent weakening and has significant consequences for MSMEs in tourist areas, which is highly dependent on tourist flows. External pressures in the form of weakened purchasing power, price fluctuations, and the depreciation of the rupiah have further suppressed MSME performance. Reports indicate that many MSMEs experienced revenue declines of 40 percent to 60 percent throughout 2024, and even up to 83 percent among MSMEs in the Pasar Seni Kujon after relocation (Kompas, 2024). Which will affect their financial flow and performance (Fitria et al., 2024; Wati et al., 2025).

The policy to relocate 1.943 MSMEs from zone II of Borobudur Temple has exacerbated the situation. The uneven relocation process resulted in more than 300 vendors not obtaining stalls. Thereby halting their business performance. Inconsistencies in the empirical findings regarding the effect of Entrepreneurial orientation on Business performance necessitate a reexamination of this phenomenon. Several studies report a positive effect of Entrepreneurial orientation (Ademilua et al., 2020; Fan et al., 2021a; Sellappan & Shanmugam, 2024; Yadav et al., 2024), whereas other studies report contrasting results (Cruz Rincon, Agredo Diaz, and Puente 2023; Soares and Perin 2019). Some scholars emphasize Innovation capability as a mediator between Entrepreneurial orientation and Business performance (J. Ferreira et al., 2020a; Hashim et al., 2024a; Latifah et al., 2020; Sheppard, 2023; Wijaya & Rahmayanti, 2023), while others emphasize Entrepreneurial competency (Aftab et al., 2022; Al Mamun et al., 2019; M. A. Khan et al., 2021; Sellappan & Shanmugam, 2024). However, no prior study has combined both mediators simultaneously.

From a theoretical perspective, many prior studies employ the Resource Based View to explain Business performance (Aftab et al., 2022; Al Mamun et al., 2019; Fan et al., 2021b; M. A. Khan et al., 2021; Makhoulfi et al., 2021a; Pulka et al., 2021; Sellappan & Shanmugam, 2024; Yadav et al., 2024). However, the Resource Based View is considered less comprehensive because it focuses primarily on internal resources. Recent studies underscore the need to incorporate external factors such as government policy that can operate as moderating variables (Aftab et al., 2022; J. J. Ferreira et al., 2021; Pulka et al., 2021). The novelty of this study lies in the simultaneous integration of Innovation capability and Entrepreneurial competency as mediating variables, together with the use of the External environment in the form of the government relocation policy as a moderating variable. The proposed combination of the RBV and DCT is intended to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how internal and external factors interact to shape MSME Business performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Resource Based View and Dynamics Capability Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) provides a perspective that firms can develop even when operating under resource constraints (Hashim et al., 2024b). Firms endowed with unique resources and competencies are more likely to attain competitive advantage and enhanced productivity (Imran et al., 2019). Despite resource limitations, entrepreneurs can leverage available or even inferior resources to establish competitive advantage (Santo et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2017). EO is conceptualized as a resource enabling firms to respond to dynamic environments (Hashim et al. 2024; Iranmanesh et al. 2021; Yadav et al. 2024), while entrepreneurial competency and innovation capability are more accurately categorized as capabilities (Hashim et al. 2024; Iranmanesh et al. 2021; Barney, Wright, and Ketchen 2001; Lerner and Almor 2002; Wernerfelt 1984). The relevance of RBV has been empirically validated across various sectors, including manufacturing (Andersén, 2021), fast-moving consumer goods (Valaei et al., 2022), start-ups (Zahra, 2021), and handicraft (Sukaatmadja et al., 2021). Nevertheless, RBV is considered insufficiently comprehensive as it primarily

focuses on internal resources, thereby necessitating the integration of DCT as a complementary framework. Dynamic capabilities refer to a firm's ability to reconfigure and integrate skills, knowledge, and both internal and external resources to swiftly adapt to change and sustain competitive advantage (Teece et al., 1997; Teece & Pisano, 1994).

2.2 Entrepreneurial Orientation on Business Performance

EO refers to proactive behavior in seizing opportunities, innovating in response to change, and taking calculated risks (Makhloufi et al. 2021b; Choi et al. 2018; Zeffane 2014), functioning as a strategic mindset for identifying and realizing opportunities. EO is measured by Fan et al. 2021a using eight unidimensional indicators. Yadav et al. (2024) highlight that handicraft enterprises, often constrained by limited resources, must therefore innovate, adapt, or face potential failure. Moreover, extant studies consistently demonstrate the significant role of EO in enhancing BP, wherein entrepreneurial thinking can be cultivated and applied within organizations. Positive EO on BP linkages have also been confirmed broadly across SMEs, as documented by Ademilua et al. (2020); Alam et al. (2022) and Yadav et al. (2024).

H1: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive influence on Business Performance

2.3 Entrepreneurial Orientation, Innovation Capability, and Business Performance

EO is a key factor that fosters the development of IC within firms (Sellappan & Shanmugam, 2024). Prior research reinforces this positive influence of EO on IC, showing that creativity, innovativeness, risk-taking, independence, and competitive aggressiveness significantly strengthen firms' ability to innovate (Makhloufi et al., 2021b; Wijaya & Rahmayanti, 2023). This is consistent with the findings of (Kee & Rahman, 2020; Setini et al., 2020; Telagawathi et al., 2022), who conclude that higher EO translates into stronger IC. Hashim et al. (2024) define IC as encompassing creativity, critical thinking, opportunity recognition, and the competence to exploit opportunities, manage resources, launch ventures, and achieve success.

Susanti et al. (2023) emphasize economically valuable innovation, while Taleb et al. (2023) frame IC as the continuous enhancement of resources to explore new opportunities, develop products, meet market needs, and strengthen internal capacities. IC emphasizes the capacity of firms to develop innovative products aligned with market demands (Andersson et al., 2020; Sulistyono and Siyamtinah, 2016), contemporary developments, and consumer preferences (Manyati & Mutsau, 2021; Sharma & Rautela, 2022). The relationship between IC and BP remains distinct and significant (Mamun et al., 2017). This innovative mindset incorporates creativity, critical thinking, opportunity recognition, and competence (Mamun et al., 2017), enabling entrepreneurs to seize opportunities, manage resources effectively, and achieve success (Dubey, 2024).

This bridging role becomes more evident when IC is positioned as a mediator between EO and BP. Prior studies have revealed that the EO on BP relationship is complex and yields mixed results: while some confirm a positive association (Ademilua et al. 2020; Campbell and Park 2017; Cannavale et al. 2020; Uddin et al. 2014; Yadav et al. 2024), others report no significant effect (Cruz Rincon et al., 2023; Masa'deh et al., 2018; Soares & Perin, 2019).

These variations indicate that EO alone may be insufficient to drive superior performance without complementary strategies and IC (Cruz Rincon et al., 2023). Innovation thus becomes the critical mechanism that transforms EO into concrete actions that enhance competitiveness (Cruz Rincon et al., 2023; Sheppard, 2023).

Through continuous innovation, firms can improve operational efficiency while simultaneously creating opportunities for market expansion. In line with Ferreira et al. (2020) and (Fang et al., 2022), IC has been shown to exert a positive impact on SME performance, serving as a vital mediator in the EO on BP relationship.

H2: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive influence on Innovation Capability

H3: Innovation Capability has a positive influence on Business Performance

H4: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive influence on Business Performance mediated by Innovation Capability

2.4 Entrepreneurial Orientation, Entrepreneurial Competency, and Business Performance

Al Mamun et al. (2019), in their study conducted in Malaysia, found that the proactive, innovative, and autonomy dimensions of EO exert a positive influence on EC, while risk-taking showed no significant relationship. Aftab et al. (2025) argued that innovation constitutes a specific individual capability that creates value through unique and inimitable resources, while proactiveness serves as a resource that triggers the development of EC leading to competitive advantage. Similarly, Sánchez (2013) identified risk-taking as a predictor of entrepreneurial behavior directly associated with competency. By contrast, (Fan et al., 2021a) demonstrated that all dimensions of EO positively affect EC.

Taken together, these findings indicate that entrepreneurs with strong EO are better equipped to build the competencies required to strengthen their firms' overall performance. Stephen et al. (2017) emphasized that firm growth and sustainability can be observed through the lens of EC, which are closely related to venture creation, development, and long-term performance outcomes (Nakhata, 2007). Tehseen and Ramayah (2015) described EC as an intangible capability of high value that provides SMEs in Malaysia with sustainable competitive advantage. EC encompasses skills, knowledge, values, and abilities that serve as strategic resources (Al Mamun et al., 2019). Aftab et al. (2022) emphasize EC as the capacity to initiate ventures, identify opportunities, and integrate resources.

EC entails interpersonal and creative thinking skills that create strategic opportunities for firms to improve performance (Bolarinwa & Okolocha, 2016), particularly in developing economies such as Nigeria.

The strategic positioning of EC becomes more apparent when it is considered as a mediator between EO and BP. Inconsistent findings on the direct EO on BP relationship, some studies confirming positive effects (Ademilua et al., 2020; Campbell & Park, 2017; Cannavale et al., 2020; Uddin et al., 2014; Yadav et al., 2024), while others reporting non-significant results (Cruz Rincon et al., 2023; Masa'deh et al., 2018; Soares & Perin, 2019), underscore the need

for a mediating mechanism. Mere possession of resources is insufficient; rather, the utilization of resources through unique competencies determines profitability (Aftab et al., 2022; Fan et al., 2021a). With the right competencies, entrepreneurs can better respond to market changes, foster innovation, and enhance competitiveness. Supporting this view, Al Mamun et al. (2019) and Khan et al. (2020a); Khan et al. (2020b) confirmed the positive effect of EO on EC in SMEs.

H5: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive influence on Entrepreneurial Competency

H6: Entrepreneurial Competency has a positive influence on Business Performance

H7: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a positive influence on Business Performance mediated by Entrepreneurial Competency

2.5 The Moderation Effect of External Environment

EE define as all activities influencing business operations, techniques, policies, procedures, and efforts, covering suppliers, customers, and the global community (Fu et al., 2021; Pulka et al., 2021; Sandra & Purwanto, 2017; Sulisty & Siyamtinah, 2016), as well as competitors, industries, financial institutions, labor markets, and other factors (Pearce & Robinson, 2013). To survive in dynamic and competitive markets, firms must align internal resources with external conditions (Nguyen et al., 2019), as successful organizations consistently adjust their strategies to environmental shifts (Dari & Isfianadewi, 2020). For SMEs in Indonesia, government relocation policies have become a major external factor that stimulates creativity and product quality, thereby enhancing competitiveness (Gyedu et al., 2021).

The external environment also reinforces the link between EO and BP. Government relocation policies affect not only business location but also financing, marketing, and property rights (Hunt, 2015). Supportive policies enable SMEs to access resources, while a lack of institutional support constrains growth (Khoshmaram et al., 2020). Previous studies (Aftab et al., 2022; Kyal et al., 2022; Nakku et al., 2020; Zhai et al., 2018) show that such policies help entrepreneurs absorb new knowledge, foster product innovation, and develop proactive behavior, all of which improve performance (Aftab et al., 2022; Kyal et al., 2022; Nakku et al., 2020; Zhai et al., 2018).

EO is thus more effectively implemented when supported by conducive external conditions, enhancing firms' ability to confront market challenges (Martins and Rialp 2013; Jabeen and Mahmood, 2014). Furthermore, the EE moderates the relationship between EC and BP. SMEs must align internal resources with environmental dynamics in order to respond effectively to market needs (Pulka et al., 2021).

Dynamic environments present both opportunities and threats, demanding high levels of flexibility and adaptability (Li et al., 2014). Aftab et al. (2025) emphasized that the EE serves as a critical contingency factor in the EC and BP nexus, particularly in developing economies. Supportive regulations and conducive business settings allow EC to be fully mobilized for performance improvement. Prior studies further confirm this moderating role, showing that the EE strengthens factors influencing BP (Joseph et al., 2022; Kaluarachchige et al., 2021;

MOSONIK et al., 2024).

H8: External Environment moderate the positive influence from Innovation Capability towards Business Performance

H9: External Environment moderate the positive influence from Entrepreneurial Orientation towards Business Performance

H10: External Environment moderate the positive influence from Entrepreneurial Competency towards Business Performance

Fig 1: Research Conceptual Model

Source: Author, 2025

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a positivist paradigm with an explanatory approach grounded in quantitative methods to analyze the causal relationship between variables (Djamba & Neuman, 2002; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Primary data were collected via a digital survey using Google Forms with a closed-ended questionnaire employing a five-point Likert scale (Hair et al., 2020; Sugiyono, 2016; Taylor-Ide & Taylor, 1995).

The research setting is field-based and non-experimental. The research population comprises all 1,943 MSMEs in the Kujon Market in Indonesia which affected by the relocation policy (Kompas, 2024; Sekaran & Bougie, 2016), Hence, this research is using probabilistic simple random sampling with the Slovin formula (5% margin of error), the data successfully collected amounted to 340 respondents. Data collected for this study can be accessed through bit.ly/RespondentMSMEs.

This study's instrument includes five main variables. BP is measured with seven unidimensional indicators from Sellappan and Shanmugam (2024): revenue growth, profit, market share, ROI, competitive position, employee morale, and business image. EO from Fan et al. (2021) uses seven indicators: innovation priority, new approaches, risk-taking, product development, market pioneering, innovation superiority, and market leader position. IC from Fan et al. (2021) has five indicators: new ideas, innovation funding, creativity, market position, and innovation frequency. EC from Aftab et al. (2025) employs six indicators: networking, negotiation, adaptability, strategy identification, and managerial competence. EE from Sellappan and Shanmugam (2024) applies eight indicators from Pati et al. (2018): competitor uncertainty, demand changes, customer preferences, and instability economic, technological, social, or political factors.

4. RESULTS

Data collection yielded 366 responses via Google Forms, with 340 retained for analysis after excluding 26 non-target cases. Demographic analysis shows that most entrepreneurs are over 35 years old (84%), have operated for more than six years (85%), and are evenly distributed by gender (54% male; 45% female). Education is predominantly elementary (47%) and junior high school (32%), with business types comprising food and beverages (36%), apparel (30%), and handicrafts (33%). All respondents earn under IDR 2 billion annually, and 94% have no employees.

4.1 Measurement Model Analysis

Referring to Hair et al. (2021), Indicator reliability was assessed by squaring standardized outer loadings, with a threshold of ≥ 0.708 (explaining at least 50% of variance). All indicators for BP, EO, IC, EC, and EE exceeded this benchmark, ranging from the lowest (EC2 = 0.713) to the highest (EE1 = 0.980), confirming acceptable reliability. Construct reliability was further supported as Cronbach's Alpha, Rho_a , and composite reliability for all variables were above 0.7, satisfying the guideline $CA \leq Rho_a \leq Rho_c$. Composite reliability ranged from 0.906 (EC) to 0.990 (EE), demonstrating excellent instrument reliability overall (Hair et al., 2022).

Table 1: Result of Indicator and Internal Consistency Reliability

Variable	Indicators	Indicator Reliability	Internal Consistency Reliability		
		FL	CA	Rho A	Rho C
Business Performance	BP1	0.887	0.950	0.953	0.959
	BP2	0.886			
	BP3	0.880			
	BP4	0.906			
	BP5	0.897			
	BP6	0.898			
	BP7	0.790			
Entrepreneurial Orientation	EO1	0.844	0.922	0.928	0.938
	EO2	0.854			
	EO3	0.797			
	EO4	0.878			

	EO5	0.843			
	EO6	0.790			
	EO7	0.772			
Innovation Capability	IC1	0.936	0.959	0.960	0.969
	IC2	0.922			
	IC4	0.934			
	IC5	0.922			
	IC6	0.923			
Entrepreneurial Competency	EC1	0.770	0.878	0.890	0.906
	EC2	0.713			
	EC3	0.852			
	EC4	0.739			
	EC5	0.846			
	EC6	0.786			
External Environment	EE1	0.980	0.988	0.988	0.990
	EE2	0.967			
	EE3	0.943			
	EE4	0.963			
	EE5	0.971			
	EE6	0.962			
	EE7	0.941			
	EE8	0.959			

Table 2: Result of Convergent and Discriminant Validity

Construct	Convergent Validity	Discriminant Validity			
		Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)			
	AVE	BP	EC	EO	EE
BP	0.772				
EC	0.618	0.511			
EO	0.682	0.144	0.106		
EE	0.923	0.079	0.072	0.715	
IC	0.860	0.110	0.118	0.761	0.631

Convergent validity assesses the extent to which items within a construct are positively correlated, commonly measured using AVE, with values >0.50 deemed adequate (Hair et al., 2020). As shown in Table 2, all variables have AVE >0.60, exceeding the 0.50 threshold, with EE highest at 0.923 and EC lowest at 0.618 both indicating strong convergent validity (Hair et al., 2020). Table 2 shows all HTMT values <0.90, indicating sufficient discriminant validity.

4.2 Structural Model Analysis

Table 3 shows that the Estimated Model performs slightly worse than the Saturated Model, with SRMR at 0.065 versus 0.081 (good fit <0.08), higher d_ ULS and d_ G values, and Chi-square and NFI of 0.737 versus 0.740 (good fit >0.90; both <0.80 indicating poor fit). Nonetheless, these marginal differences suggest only a minor decline, indicating the proposed model remains reasonably adequate (Hair et al., 2021). The Estimated Model demonstrates slightly lower fit than the Saturated Model, primarily due to SRMR slightly exceeding the threshold and low NFI, yet the differences are minimal, rendering the model is acceptable.

Table 3: Result of Model Fit

Category	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.065	0.081
d ULS	2.354	3.645
d G	2.749	2.813
Chi-square	4301.743	4347.158
NFI	0.740	0.737

Table 4: Result of Hypothesis, Collinearity Statistics, and Effect Size

Hypothesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	STDEV	T statistics	P values	VIF	F2	Result
Direct Path								
H1: EO -> BP	0.038	0.032	0.063	0.596	0.551	2.322	0.001	Rejected
H2: EO -> IC	0.700	0.701	0.039	18.064	0.000	1.000	0.963	Supported
H3: IC -> BP	0.210	0.216	0.056	3.729	0.000	2.421	0.034	Supported
H5: EO -> EC	0.596	0.599	0.037	16.077	0.000	1.000	0.550	Supported
H6: EC -> BP	0.322	0.321	0.055	5.814	0.000	1.867	0.105	Supported
Indirect Path								
H4: EO-> IC -> BP	0.147	0.152	0.042	3.474	0.001	-		Supported
H5: EO -> EC -> BP	0.192	0.192	0.035	5.520	0.000	-		Supported
Moderation Path								
H8: EE x IC -> BP	-0.182	-0.194	0.073	2.502	0.012	3.102	0.023	Supported
H9: EE x EO -> BP	0.084	0.095	0.059	1.410	0.159	2.192	0.008	Rejected
H10: EE x EC -> BP	-0.141	-0.139	0.071	1.988	0.047	2.696	0.015	Supported

Collinearity testing shows that all VIF values fall between 1.000 and 3.102, below the critical threshold of 5, confirming the absence of multicollinearity. Effect size (f^2) results indicate that EO→BP (0.001) is negligible, IC→BP (0.034) is small, EC→BP (0.105) is moderate, EO→EC (0.550) is strong, and EO→IC (0.963) is very strong. Moderation effects of EE are minimal, with EE*(IC→BP) at 0.023, EE*(EO→BP) at 0.008, and EE*(EC→BP) at 0.015. Bootstrapping with the BCa method confirms eight hypotheses accepted and two rejected: H1 ($p=0.551$, $T=0.596$) and H9 ($p=0.159$, $T=1.410$) were rejected, while H2–H8 and H10 were supported with significant p-values and T-statistics above 1.96.

5. DISCUSSION

The first hypothesis test shows EO has no significant effect on BP, consistent with Mathafena et al. (2023), Cruz Rincon et al. (2023), and (Soares & Perin, 2019), who found EO does not always directly influence business performance. This creates a gap between orientation and actual performance, aligning with Omowole et al. (2024) that relocated MSMEs rarely prioritize innovation strategically. From an RBV perspective (Barney et al., 2001), EO as an intangible resource requires complementary resources, policy support, technology, and market access, and must be combined with competency and innovation to improve performance. This finding can be explained by the fact that relocated MSMEs in Kujon Market face severe external disruptions, such as loss of customer access, declining revenues, and limited business

facilities, which weaken the immediate translation of entrepreneurial orientation into measurable business outcomes. In this context, EO alone is insufficient to improve performance unless it is converted into concrete capabilities such as innovation and competency that help MSMEs adapt to unstable environments and policy-induced challenges.

Hypothesis 2 results show EO has a positive and significant effect on IC, consistent with Makhoulfi et al. (2021), Setini et al. 2020; Wijaya and Rahmayanti 2023), who found high-EO entrepreneurs possess stronger innovative capacity. The EO on IC path is stronger than EO on EC, indicating entrepreneurial drive more strongly fosters idea exploration and creative solutions, especially post-relocation (Yodchai et al., 2022). EO as a strategic intangible resource shapes capability, with IC meeting VRIN criteria, making MSME products unique and hard to replicate, positioning EO as a capability enabler rather than an end factor. Hypothesis 3 results show IC has a positive and significant effect on BP among relocated Kujon Market MSMEs, consistent with (Al Mamun et al., 2019; Andersson et al., 2020; Fang et al., 2022), who highlight innovation's role in sustaining performance in dynamic environments. However, IC's contribution to BP is weaker than EC's, as innovations are often incremental (e.g., packaging or color changes) without major process or business model shifts, limiting impact (González-Varona et al., 2021). This requires valuable, rare, and non-substitutable innovations (Hashim et al., 2024) and (Iranmanesh et al., 2021), Hypothesis 4 results confirm IC as a full mediator between EO and BP, where EO, having no direct effect, significantly influences BP only when transformed into IC. This supports Fang et al. (2022), Ferreira et al. (2020), Sheppard (2023), who assert EO boosts BP effectively via innovation. EO should be channeled into innovative actions such as new product development, alternative sales channels, or strengthening local narratives (Nsereko et al., 2021). Although IC's mediating role is weaker than EC's, it remains strategic for MSMEs with limited managerial capacity (Sellappan & Shanmugam, 2024). Hypothesis 5 results show EO has a positive and significant effect on EC among relocated Kujon Market MSME owners, aligning with Aftab et al. (2025), Khan et al. (2020), Al Mamun et al. (2019), who highlight EO's role in strengthening market understanding, decision-making, adaptability, and strategic relationship-building. EO's impact on EC is stronger than on IC, influenced by a demographic profile that is predominantly older, less educated, and running traditional, adaptation-focused businesses.

Hypothesis 6 results show EC has a positive and significant effect on BP, aligning with Bolarinwa and Okolocha (2016), Al Mamun et al. (2019), Tehseen and Ramayah (2015), who note that entrepreneurial competency includes technical and managerial skills, social networking, negotiation, market intuition, and decision-making under uncertainty. For forcibly relocated Kujon Market MSMEs, EC is the main differentiator between survival and failure, with opportunity recognition as the most representative indicator, especially amid customer loss, revenue decline, and loss of premises (Fazal et al., 2022; González-Varona et al., 2021). The results of Hypothesis 7 show that EC is a significant mediator in the EO–BP relationship among relocated Kujon Market MSMEs, where EO has no direct effect on BP (H1 rejected) but exerts a significant indirect effect through EC, indicating full mediation (Aftab et al., 2025; S. Khan, Rathore, et al., 2020; Sellappan & Shanmugam, 2024). This finding confirms that EO impacts performance only when translated into functional competencies, particularly amid

declining revenues, customer loss, and rising distribution costs, where negotiation, stakeholder engagement, and vendor collaboration become critical.

The findings indicate that EE negatively moderates the IC on BP relationship, meaning that under unstable external conditions, IC's effectiveness in driving performance declines, consistent with Fu et al. (2021), Gyedu et al. (2021), Khoshmaram et al. (2020).

Market uncertainty, relocation policies, and disrupted customer access hinder product or service innovation (Chibani, 2024), particularly for Kujon Market MSMEs, most of whom are low-educated and operate conventionally. Conversely, EE does not moderate the EO on BP relationship, diverging from Jabeen and Mahmood (2014), Martins and Rialp (2013), and Zhai et al. (2018), as MSME owners tend to rely on internal control factors such as risk-taking and personal experience despite drastic environmental changes. EE also negatively moderates the EC on BP relationship, aligning with Aftab et al. (2025), Joseph et al. (2022), and Pulka et al. (2021), where high competency cannot be fully leveraged due to external constraints such as relocation and disrupted consumer access.

6. CONCLUSION

As to conclude EO has no direct effect on BP but positively influences IC and EC, which act as full mediators. IC exerts a positive yet modest effect on BP, while EC has a stronger impact, serving as the primary pathway for converting EO into business performance. EE negatively moderates the IC on BP and EC on BP relationships, indicating that environmental instability weakens the role of innovation and competency, whereas the EO–BP remains unaffected by EE as MSME owners rely more on internal control. This study recommends that MSMEs strengthen EO through IC and EC, as EO alone does not directly impact BP without conversion into these capabilities (Aftab et al. 2025; Fang et al. 2022; Ferreira et al. 2020; Khan et al. 2020; Sellappan and Shanmugam 2024; Sheppard 2023). Enhancing IC requires incentives, funding, training, and digital technology, while EC, particularly negotiation skills, demands practical training and mentoring. Government intervention should focus on planned relocation policies, facility provision, and innovation-driven, collaborative, and technology-based adaptation to sustain MSME performance.

This study is limited to MSMEs in the Kujon Art Market, Borobudur, and thus its findings cannot be generalized to all MSME sectors in Indonesia. Future research should broaden the scope to capture more diverse phenomena and explore additional factors such as social capital and digital capability, both of which are critical for MSME recovery post-disruption (Affandi et al., 2024; Kurniasari et al., 2023; Olamide & Ogbechie, 2021; Van Tran et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023). This study also identifies potential self-assessment bias, particularly in the IC variable, as responses were provided by participants with relatively low educational backgrounds. Future research should employ more precise measurement tools and mixed-method approaches to minimize bias and produce a more comprehensive analysis. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design limits the measurement of dynamic variables such as attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors; thus, similar studies are recommended to adopt a longitudinal design for more authentic and in-depth findings.

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Disclosure Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The dataset generated and analyzed during the current study is available at [bit.ly/Respondent MSME](https://bit.ly/RespondentMSME)

Authorship Contribution

Awang Pradika Sudyanto: Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing – original draft. Oshel Arie Utama: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. Prahega Raih Khatrisna: Methodology, Project administration, Data curation, Writing – original draft. Chrisanty Victoria Layman: Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

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